

Post-test survey for learners (Aasis)

Thank you for participation! Now please answer background information questions and give feedback!

1. Your research ID (e.g. 123)

Your background information

2. Gender

3. Age

4. What is your first language? If you feel that you have more than one first language, please mention which languages.

5. Which other languages can you speak in such a way that you can use them to cope with everyday situations?

Albanian

Arabic

Bengali

- Dari
- English
- Spanish
- Italian
- Chinese
- Kurdish
- Nepalese
- Portuguese
- Polish
- French
- Romanian
- German
- Somali
- Finnish
- Thai
- Turkish
- Ukrainian
- Hungarian
- Urdu
- Russian
- Vietnamese
- Estonian
- Other, please specify
- Swedish

6. Self-assessment of my level in spoken production in Finnish (see descriptions below)

- A1
- A2

- B1
- B2
- C1
- C2

Spoken production, level descriptions (CEFR self-assessment grids)

A1: I can use simple phrases and sentences to describe where I live and people I know.

A2: I can use a series of phrases and sentences to describe in simple terms my family and other people, living conditions, my educational background and my present or most recent job.

B1: I can connect phrases in a simple way in order to describe experiences and events, my dreams, hopes and ambitions. I can briefly give reasons and explanations for opinions and plans. I can narrate a story or relate the plot of a book or film and describe my reactions

B2: I can present clear, detailed descriptions on a wide range of subjects related to my field of interest. I can explain a viewpoint on a topical issue giving the advantages and disadvantages of various options.

C1: I can present clear, detailed descriptions of complex subjects integrating sub-themes, developing particular points and rounding off with an appropriate conclusion.

C2: I can present a clear, smoothly-flowing description or argument in a style appropriate to the context and with an effective logical structure which helps the recipient to notice and remember significant points.

7. Self-assessment of my level in spoken interaction in Finnish (see descriptions below)

- A1
- A2
- B1
- B2
- C1
- C2

Spoken interaction, level descriptions (CEFR self-assessment grids)

A1: I can interact in a simple way provided the other person is prepared to repeat or rephrase things at a slower rate of speech and help me formulate what I'm trying to say. I can ask and answer simple questions in areas of immediate need or on very familiar topics.

A2: I can communicate in simple and routine tasks requiring a simple and direct exchange of information on familiar topics and activities. I can handle very short social exchanges, even though I can't usually understand enough to keep the conversation going myself.

B1: I can deal with most situations likely to arise whilst travelling in an area where the language is spoken. I can enter unprepared into conversation on topics that are familiar, of personal interest or pertinent to everyday life (e.g. family, hobbies, work, travel and current events).

B2: I can interact with a degree of fluency and spontaneity that makes regular interaction with native speakers quite possible. I can take an active part in discussion in familiar contexts, accounting for and sustaining my views.

C1: I can express myself fluently and spontaneously without much obvious searching for expressions. I can use language flexibly and effectively for social and professional purposes. I can formulate ideas and opinions with precision and relate my contribution skilfully to those of other speakers.

C2: I can take part effortlessly in any conversation or discussion and have a good familiarity with idiomatic expressions and colloquialisms. I can express myself fluently and convey finer shades of meaning precisely. If I do have a problem I can backtrack and restructure around the difficulty so smoothly that other people are hardly aware of it.

Views on the speaking test

8. What is your impression of the test?

	1 Very positive	2 Positive	3 Not positive nor negative	4 Negative	5 Very negative
	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

9. What do you think about the content of the test?

	1 Completely disagree	2 Quite disagree	3 Neither agree nor disagree	4 Quite agree	5 Completely agree
A) The instructions were clear and I understood what I was expected to do in the test.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
B) It was easy for me to understand the materials (texts, pictures, recordings) that appeared in the tasks.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	1 Completely disagree	2 Quite disagree	3 Neither agree nor disagree	4 Quite agree	5 Completely agree
C) The topics of the tasks interested me.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
D) I learned something new.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
E) The test tasks reminded everyday situations.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
F) The exam tested the skills I have practiced during Finnish lessons.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
G) The test was the right length for me.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
H) The test tasks were of an appropriate level for me.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I) Completing these tasks gives a true picture of my oral language skills.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

10. What do you think about the tasks?

11. Did you encounter any technical problems?

12. Is there anything else worth mentioning?

Views on automated assessment

13. Would you be worried if you knew that your test performance was being assessed by a computer instead of a human?

Yes

No

14. What do you think are the advantages and benefits of automated assessment?

15. What do you think are the disadvantages or threats of automated assessment?

16. What would you like to ask about automated assessment?

17. Here you can complete the answers or give feedback

Submit